

BR-IRGA plantings in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil

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BR-IRGA 409 and 410 are the new names for P790-B4-4-1T (IR930-2/IR665-31-1-4) and P798-B4-4-1T (IR930-53/IR665-31-2), two semidwarf lines developed at the International Tropical Agricultural Center (CIAT) in Colombia. They were introduced, selected, and released in 1978 and 1980 through the Rio Grande do Sul Rice Research Station, USAID, and the UEPAE-Pelotas/EMBRAPA rice research team.

Both varieties are between 100 and

Area, rice production, and yield of BR-IRGA 409 and BR-IRGA 410, 1979-84, Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil.

Year	Area planted					Statewide	
	Total (thousand ha)	BR-IRGA 409 (thousand ha)	Proportion of total rice area (%)	BR-IRGA 410 (thousand ha)	Proportion of total rice area (%)	Production (million t)	Yield (t/ha)
1979-80	590	.45	.76	.028	.0047	2.183	3.7
1980-81	589	9.77	1.66	8.34	.142	2.356	4.0
1981-82	607	212.44	35.0	18.21	3.0	2.489	4.1
1982-83	670	435.22	65.0	33.48	5.0	2.479	3.7 ^a
1983-84	704	457.58	65.0	35.2	5.0	3.168	4.5

^a Flooding and low temperature damage.

110 cm tall, have long slender grains, mature in 110 to 130 d, and tolerate blast and Helminthosporium leaf spot. In 1983-84, BR-IRGA 409 was planted on 457,580 ha or 65% of the rice area in Rio Grande do Sul (see table).

In 5 yr, rice production in Rio Grande do Sul has increased about 50% partly as the result of increased area planted to rice, and also because of introduced varieties. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Lodging of rice cultivars grown in pure and mixed stands at different fertility levels

D. C. Ghosh, associate professor of agronomy, Birsa Agricultural University, Kanke, Ranchi, Bihar; and M. Maji, College of Agriculture, Visva-Bharati, West Bengal, India

We studied the lodging behavior of tall and semidwarf rices grown in pure and mixed field stands at different fertility levels in 1979 and 1980 kharif. Soil was a

lateritic acid with pH 6.0, 0.22% organic carbon, 0.02% total N, 9 kg P/ha, and 132 kg K/ha. The experiment was in a split-plot design with 3 replications and 4 fertility levels: no fertilizer control (F₀), 50-13-25 (F₁), 100-26-50 (F₂), and 150-40-75 (F₃) kg NPK/ha. Fertility levels were in main plots and rice cultivars and mixed stands in subplots. Semidwarf Pankaj and tall Mahsuri were grown. The mixed stand was obtained by planting two center rows of Mahsuri bounded by single rows of Pankaj, which gave a prismatic shape to the crop canopy. The crop

received adequate weed, insect, and disease protection and was irrigated when necessary. Light transmission rate (LTR) at different growth stages and plant height at flowering were measured. Percentage of lodged area in each plot was recorded after flowering.

The pure stand of Mahsuri was more susceptible to lodging (see table) than Pankaj. Lodging increased with fertilizer application. Pure and mixed stands of Pankaj lodged only at the highest fertility level. Height of both tall and semidwarf cultivars was significantly less in the mixed

Lodging incidence and plant height of rice cultivars grown in pure and mixed stands.

Fertility level (kg NPK)	Incidence of lodging (%)						Plant height (cm) at flowering ^a			
	1979			1980			Pure stand		Mixed stand	
	Pankaj	Mahsuri	Mixed stand	Pankaj	Mahsuri	Mixed stand	Pankaj	Mahsuri	Pankaj	Mahsuri
0- 0- 0 (control)	0	0	0	0	0	0	80	100	76	97
50-13-25	0	9	0	0	5	0	95	120	89	112
120-26-50	0	70	0	0	65	0	104	126	96	118
150-40-75	16	94	9	10	91	6	109	130	99	118
Mean							97	119	90	111
CD at 5%	Cultivars and stand = 4.0, Fertility = 6.6									

^a Av of 2 yr.

stand than in pure stands at all fertility levels except at zero added fertilizer. Higher fertility levels significantly increased plant height of both cultivars. The prismatic shape of the mixed stand canopy allowed more light to reach the plants and resulted in greater LTR than in pure stands of both cultivars at all growth stages (see figure). LTR was least in Mahsuri pure stand. LTR decreased gradually as fertility levels increased and decreased more in pure than in mixed stands. □

LTR in rice cultivars grown in pure and mixed stands at different fertility levels.

Dormancy of IR50 seeds

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IR50 seeds obtained at harvest were evaluated for dormancy. Immediately after harvest, they had 14.7% moisture and 15% germination. But when stained with a 0.25% solution of tetra-zolium chloride, the seeds showed 92% germinability, which indicated the presence of dormancy.

The seeds were sun-dried for 3 d from 0930 to 1130 h and from 1400 to 1700 h, shade-dried, or dried at 40°C in a hot-air dryer. Moisture content and percentage germination were recorded 1, 7, 14, and 27 d after harvest (see table).

At 14 and 27 d after harvest, shade-dried seeds were soaked in water for 24 h and tested for germination (see table). □

Moisture content and gemination of IR50 seeds at different days after harvest, Coimbatore, India.

Days after harvest	Drying treatment	Moisture content (%)	Germination (%)
Fresh	—	15	15
	Sun	12	22
	Shade	13	20
	At 40°C	13	26
7	Sun	9	85
	Shade	10	25
	At 40°C	9	70
	Soaking and leaching of shade-dried seed	—	78
14	Sun	10	87
	Shade	10	44
	At 40°C	10	86
	Soaking and leaching of shade-dried seed	—	83
27	Sun	9	85
	Shade	10	82
	At 40°C	10	83
	Soaking and leaching of shade-dried seed	—	83
CD (0.05)		3	4

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Comparative biology, pathology, and karyology of rice and maize isolates of *Rhizoctonia solani* f. sp. *sasakii*

S. C. Ahuja, *plant pathologist, Rice Research Station, Kaul; and M. M. Payak, head, Division of Mycology and Plant Pathology, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012, India*

We compared six Indian isolates of maize and rice sheath blight (ShB) pathogen

R. solani f. sp. *sasakii*, collected from Karnal (R₁), Solan (R₂), Sundernagar (R₃), Bajaura (R₄), Hyderabad (R₅), and Coimbatore (R₆). We evaluated range of nuclei, mean and mode of nuclear number per hyphal cell, in vitro response to temperature, fungicide and antibiotic response, and relationship of temperature levels to disease intensity.

We found that rice and maize ShB pathogens were identical based on

positive cross-inoculation of the pathogen isolates; symptom similarity on *Saccharum officinarum*, *Paspalum scorbiculatum*, *Pennisetum purpureum*, *Zea maxicana*, *Zea mays* (varieties *indurata*, *indentata*, *saccharata*, and *everta*), *Setaria italica*, *Panicum miliaceum*, *Sorghum vulgare*, *Echinochloa frumentacea*, and *Pennisetum americanum*; similar sclerotial and mycelial characters; nuclear mode number (see table); similar range of